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Executive summary

Deliverable D6.3 presents the outcomes of two pilot courses in Slovakia and Portugal that applied the Learning by Developing (LbD) model to tackle real urban challenges.

The UNIZA pilot engaged students in a blended course combining online learning with on-site activities, supported by local stakeholders. Participants developed practical solutions aligned with Inclusive Sustainable and Resilient (ISR) city themes and received feedback from municipal authorities. The pilot demonstrated strong ecosystem involvement, high participant satisfaction, and progress toward ECTS harmonisation. Insights from this implementation will guide future improvements and support the scaling of ISR education across widening countries.

The ISCTE Pilot followed the same principles of the UNIZA pilot, regarding the LbD implementation, the combination of online learning with on-site activities and the active participation of local InCITIES Associated Partners stakeholders (national and private companies, NGO's and municipalities). The Associated Partners proposed challenges were completely aligned with ISR city themes and were enthusiastically addressed by the different student groups. The realization of a Hackathon, in the last day of the onsite week, was an opportunity to involve all the participants, e.g., students, associated partner representatives, professors and tutors, in a single event.

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1 Introduction

The **purpose** of this document, characterised as a **demonstrator-type deliverable**, is to showcase the practical implementation, results, and learnings from the two pilots in a visually appealing and evidence-based format. The current Deliverable 6.3 is framed within WP6 task 6.3 objectives, linked to various other tasks of WP5 and WP6. Task 6.3 aims to integrate the bottom-up Learning by Developing (LbD) approach (T6.1) with the knowledge base from T6.2 to address urban challenges in Portugal and Slovakia. The two pilots support ISR curriculum development, joint degrees (T5.1), and ECTS harmonisation (T5.3), with a strong focus on ecosystem participation.

The pilot schools aim to implement a ‘proof-of-concept’ that jointly achieve the following key goals within WP6:

1. to develop capacity and experiences on teaching topics relevant for a **transition towards Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient (ISR) cities**, as delineated by the 7 themes of WP2 (the ‘what’);
2. to achieve a shared understanding and practical experience in implementing the **LbD pedagogical model**, which requires pilots to be based on a “authentic real-life assignment” (the ‘how’);
3. to attract both **instructors and students from InCITIES partners** by making use of existing EU mechanisms for researcher and student mobility (the ‘who’), and;
4. doing so while monitoring and **collecting lessons learned** to include later in the deliverable D6.4 for ensuring continuous learning throughout pilot implementation, including particularly LbD learnings, ISR learnings for WP2 feedback, and administrative learnings for WP5 feedback.

Deliverable 6.3 addresses WP6 **goal #3**, which aims to attract both **instructors and students from InCITIES partners** by making use of existing EU mechanisms for researcher and student mobility (the ‘who’). Goal #4 will be detailed in the final lessons learned and outlook (D6.4 in M36).

The deliverable 6.3 reports on the **implementation of the LbD pedagogical model in pilot demonstrators (in the form of trainings) in the participating widening countries (Slovakia + Portugal)**.

Both the 2 pilots were implemented as Erasmus+ Blended Intensive Programme involving teachers and students from both UNIZA and ISCTE and other InCITIES Universities, applying a joint degree approach. The 2 pilots provided ECTS accreditation to the participant students.

The structure of this document is as follows: Section 2 of this document outlines the pilots at UNIZA in Slovakia and ISCTE in Portugal, focusing on their objectives, implementation, and

stakeholder engagement. In the case of the UNIZA pilot, it is also provided the key outcomes, including the development of ISR curricula, ECTS harmonisation, solutions for urban challenges, and highlights key insights from the pilot, proposed adjustments for future iterations, and recommendations for scaling or replication in other widening countries. In the case of the ISCTE pilot these insights will be included in D6.4.

Section 3 concludes by summarising the pilots' contributions and their alignment with the overall project objectives, emphasising the impact on ISR education and ecosystem collaboration. Finally, in Appendix A, we provide evidences of the UNIZA BIP pilot student assignments, ISCTE Erasmus+ Blended Intensive Programme pilot with challenges provided by InCITIES Associated Partners (APs) and one student group work at the ISCTE pilot.

2 Pilots

The iterative pilots in Portugal and Slovakia are crucial for integrating the bottom-up Learning by Developing (LbD) approach with a co-created knowledge base to address real-life urban challenges. They contribute to the development of a common Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient (ISR) curriculum, supporting joint degrees and ECTS harmonisation while fostering strong ecosystem participation through the quintuple helix model. By engaging universities, cities, businesses, citizens, and nature, these pilots enhance collaboration and ensure practical, scalable solutions for widening countries.

Readers can refer to **Deliverable D6.2** for the LbD pedagogical model and learning materials used in the UNIZA and ISCTE pilots. Furthermore, D6.2 outlines the pilot plan, methodology, and strategies for organising Summer and Winter school training events, which inform the implementation of the iterative pilots in D6.3. It also provides guidance on securing partners, addressing constraints, and fostering interactive, multidisciplinary learning environments, all of which support the ecosystem participation and practical rollout of the pilots in widening countries.

Both pilots adopted authentic real-life assignments with local stakeholders (APs) involved in the pilots. This facilitated a better understanding of case-specific challenges, encouraged active participation from all relevant stakeholders and enabled a more targeted application of the LbD pedagogical model. The LbD model was applied throughout the entire duration of the pilots, gradually equipping students with personally developed skills to tackle problems and suggest creative solutions.

Due to the different timings of the 2 pilots at UNIZA and ISCTE, the content of the sections below differs for each. Some of the information presented for the ISCTE pilot is included in Deliverable 6.2 as outlined in section 2.1.2 below.

2.1 Pilot at UNIZA in Slovakia

2.1.1 Student attendance

A total of 33 students joined the UNIZA pilot course, actively participating in all scheduled activities. The course followed an Erasmus+ Blended Intensive Programme (BIP) format, integrating online learning with a week-long in-person component.

- **Online modules:** Students took part in 9 interactive sessions covering topics such as sustainable mobility systems, data-informed decision-making, and transport

innovation. These included live lectures, collaborative workshops, and group-based assignments.

- **On-site week:** Conducted jointly at UNIZA and the co-working space of Stanica Žilina-Záriečie, the intensive in-person week enabled students to engage directly with stakeholders, take part in field visits, and present their proposals to local authorities and peers.

Table 1 below summarises the fields of study of participants in the UNIZA pilot, grouped and sorted by frequency. The most common backgrounds are in Computer Science, Informatics, and Software Development (9 participants), followed by Management and Business-related fields (6 participants), and Transportation and Mobility (6 participants). Other participants have expertise in various branches of Engineering (5), Digital and Educational Technologies (4), as well as Cybersecurity, Public Policy, and Healthcare Technologies. This diverse mix highlights the interdisciplinary nature of the pilot and its relevance across both technical and socio-economic domains.

Figure 1: Online course No.1 on Sustainable Mobility Principles

Table 1: Fields of study among UNIZA course participants

Field of Study	Count	Disciplines
Computer Science / Informatics / Software Development	9	Computer Science, Informatics, Telecommunication and Computer Science, Software and App Development, Informatics and Business Systems, Applied Mathematics and Digital Technologies, Mathematics Applied and Digital Technologies, Computer Science (AI) applied to transportation, Computer Science and Business Management, Technologies in Healthcare
Management & Business	6	Management, Supply Chain and Operations Management, Computer Science and Business Management, Economy of Service, Marketing
Transportation & Mobility	6	Road transportation, Transportation, Intelligent transport systems, Safety of movement and its organisation of railway transport, Organisation of railway constructions, Computer Science (AI) applied to transportation
Engineering	5	Electric-Electronics Engineering, Automotive Engineering, Electrical and Energy Engineering, Construction Management, Management and Technology of Constructions
Educational and Digital	4	Digital Educational Technologies, Communication, Culture and Information Technologies, Management and Digital Technologies
Cybersecurity	2	Cybersecurity
Social Studies	2	Public Policy, International Studies

The course gathered students from a range of academic disciplines, institutions (Figure 5) and study levels, bachelor's, master's, and doctoral (Figure 2), creating a dynamic and interdisciplinary learning environment. Participants were from 14 countries (Figure 6) and formed multicultural teams, highlighting the global relevance of sustainable transport issues. There was also gender balance among participants, with 42% identifying as female and the remaining 58% as male. This diversity enriched peer learning and encouraged creative, collaborative problem-solving.

Figure 2: Level of education of participants

Figure 3: Groupwork at the UNIZA pilot

Figure 4: Gender allocation among participants of the UNIZA pilot

Figure 5: Institution of participants of the UNIZA pilot

Figure 6: Country of participants of the UNIZA pilot

2.1.2 Knowledge base from ISR cities

The knowledge base used to develop this course is drawn from Task 6.2, with all relevant information and materials detailed in InCITIES Deliverable D6.2 - *Learning material and pilots plan*. Particularly relevant are the following, including among others details on the case studies and course content (see D6.2 for details):

- Annex I: Practical guide to pilot course design (chapter 1: the inner development goals and soft skills, chapter 2: 7 pillars and futures thinking, chapter 3: guidance and roles, chapter 4: major key design rules, chapter 5: course and case studies with authentic challenge, chapter 6: 10 principles of the pilot course)
- Annex II: InCITIES Methodology for Pilots Execution LbD - SECI - ISR - Six Pillars Framework - Job Labs Methodology
- Annex V, VI: Case studies
- Annex XIV - Detailed plan of UNIZA pilot briefing session and course online modules

2.1.3 Activities and stakeholders

The UNIZA pilot was designed to maximise student participation and interaction through a diverse range of activities involving academic experts, local authorities, and industry partners. Key highlights included:

- **Interactive Online Sessions:** The digital component featured a variety of engaging formats, including instructor-led presentations, participant contributions, group brainstorming on virtual whiteboards, quizzes, Q&A sessions, and open discussions ensuring continuous active involvement. Warm-up activities and discussions on student expectations helped build a collaborative and motivated learning community from the outset.
- **Expert-led Presentations and Speeches:** Participants benefited from insights shared by instructors specialising in ISR thematic areas, LbD methodology, air pollution, and urban planning. Contributions also came from local authorities, architects from the UHA municipality, and researchers from DLR, enriching the learning experience with real-world perspectives.
- **Collaborative Group Work:** Throughout the course, participants worked in diverse teams to analyse challenges and develop innovative solutions, culminating in dynamic group presentations that showcased their findings and recommendations.
- **Immersive Site Visits:** Students engaged directly with the local context through guided tours of key locations such as the local bus operator DMPZ, KIA factory, and the case study areas, including a comprehensive exploration of Žilina city. These visits provided practical understanding and grounded their project work.
- **Data Collection Activities:** Students took part in hands-on data gathering exercises, such as air pollution and traffic counts, directly contributing to their case study analyses.
- **Student Solution Presentations:** The programme concluded with participants presenting their proposed solutions to representatives from the UHA and local authorities, fostering meaningful dialogue and stakeholder engagement.

Together, these activities created a vibrant, participatory environment where students, experts, and local partners collaborated closely to address sustainable mobility challenges (Figure 7). From academia, the University of Žilina (UNIZA), ISCTE, LAUREA, Gustave Eiffel University and the German Aerospace Center (DLR) supported student learning, research, and

innovation. These universities helped students develop skills for future jobs and encouraged collaboration on technology and sustainable solutions.

The local government also played an important role, including the City of Žilina, the Slovak Environment Agency, and the public transport company DPMZ. They supported the programme by sharing knowledge about urban planning, environmental protection, and transport systems. From the business and civil society side, the KIA automotive plant and the civic association OZ Mulica were involved. KIA shared insights from industry, while OZ Mulica brought the voice of citizens and promoted sustainable mobility. The entire pilot was shaped by a shared concern for both the environment and society, showing how different sectors can work together to support innovation and sustainable growth.

Figure 7: Ecosystem involvement at UNIZA BIP pilot (adjusted from the quintuple helix model¹)

¹ <https://www.paeradigms.org/post/education-for-sustainable-development>

Figure 8: Visit to KIA automotive plant

2.1.4 Feedback from participants

Overall, 93% of the UNIZA BIP pilot course participants reported that it is very likely (76%) or likely (19%) to recommend this course to colleagues or peers. The remaining 7% selected 'Neutral' as an answer to this question. The free-text feedback from participants provided valuable insights into the strengths of the course and areas for improvement. The responses highlight the effectiveness of the programme while also identifying opportunities to enhance engagement, structure, and stakeholder interaction. Some of the participant testimonials include the following:

“The team exercises were the highlight of the course – collaboration made learning truly engaging.”

“The interdisciplinary nature of the programme was a great learning experience.”

“It was a very friendly atmosphere, and I learned a lot.”

The key takeaways of participants' feedback on the UNIZA BIP pilot course are summarised in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Key takeaways of participants feedback on the UNIZA BIP course

Thematic area	Positive Feedback	Areas for Improvement
Learning Experience	Hands-on, real-life case studies & fieldwork	Ensure better integration of academic content with real-world applications
Collaboration	Interdisciplinary teamwork and knowledge sharing	More interaction with local citizens
Schedule & Structure	Well-organised, varied activities	Reduce workload and allow more time for group work
Stakeholder Involvement	Valuable engagement with city officials, planners, and academia	Earlier feedback from city planners to refine ideas
Presentations & Feedback	Opportunity to develop and present ideas	Make presentations less repetitive and more practical.
Social & Networking	Friendly atmosphere, networking with students and professionals	Provide clearer presentation guidelines and expectations

Students were motivated by the chance to gain new knowledge on sustainable mobility, improve English and soft skills, and connect with international peers. Many also saw the programme as valuable for their future careers. Participants found the international collaboration engaging and insightful, though some noted uneven participation in group work. Participants deepened their understanding of urban planning, sustainable transport, and project-based work. They also developed skills in international teamwork and public speaking.

“I learnt that implementing solutions is much more complex than it seems.”

Students appreciated the diverse topics, practical focus, and sense of community. The on-site week in Žilina was a highlight.

“It was a bonding experience, and the city is even considering our suggestions.”

Based on the feedback received from participants; to enhance practical engagement, the course should incorporate more hands-on activities while reducing repetitive presentations. A balanced schedule, combining structured sessions with flexible group work time, would improve the learning experience as reported by a couple of participants. It was also mentioned by one student that direct interaction with local residents would further enrich

the real-world application of ideas, while another student stated that involving city planners earlier in the process would ensure better alignment of project concepts. Additionally, providing clearer presentation guidelines and continuous feedback from instructors and stakeholders would support students in refining their proposals effectively.

These insights will inform the planning of future iterations of the BIP course, ensuring a more engaging and impactful learning experience for participants. While this feedback highlights valuable lessons learned, the majority of respondents to the evaluation form reported a very good experience and positive learning outcomes.

2.1.5 How the 10 LbD principles were implemented in the UNIZA pilot

The UNIZA pilot applied the 10 LbD principles, as those described in Annex 1 of the deliverable D6.2, to enhance learning through clear objectives, tailored student grouping, and a blended learning approach. Engaging, research-based materials supported active participation, teamwork, and problem-solving. A supportive environment fostered open discussions, continuous assessment, and timely feedback, ensuring fair evaluation and student progress. Table 3 below demonstrates how the 10 principles for designing a pilot course were applied on the UNIZA pilot.

Table 3: Application of the 10 Principles on the UNIZA Pilot

#	Principle	Application in the UNIZA Pilot
1	Clear Objectives and Learning Outcomes	Objectives were well-defined prior to the BIP course; for each one of the online courses and the onsite week activities. These were adjusted to fit the competence level of participants and connected to the 2 real-life case studies.
2	Assessment of Initial Student Competence	Student backgrounds (motivation, short bio, degree, field of study, nationality) were evaluated to tailor the learning experience and select appropriate methods. Groups of participants were formed ensuring a balance of skills and demographic characteristics across them.
3	Blended Learning Approach	A mix of online and on-site methods, including lectures, teamwork, and problem-solving exercises, was used to enhance engagement and knowledge acquisition. Participants worked in groups and were actively engaged in creative thinking and ideas development.
4	Student Activation and Motivation	Active participation was encouraged through hands-on assignments, research, and collaboration with professionals, fostering creativity and practical problem-solving. Continuous communication ensured their alertness and preparedness.

5	High-Quality Course Content	Learning materials were up-to-date, research-based, and linked to real-world urban challenges, ensuring relevance and interdisciplinary collaboration.
6	Comprehensible and Attractive Educational Material	Materials were structured, engaging, and accessible prior to each course. Courses incorporated diverse educational methods such as group work, online polls, voluntary participation, presentations by participants etc., to support different learning styles and maintain student interest.
7	Supportive and Inclusive Learning Atmosphere	A collaborative and secure environment was fostered, promoting teamwork, open discussions, and knowledge-sharing between students, teachers, and stakeholders. Sessions for open discussion and questions were provided frequently.
8	Continuous Assessment and Learning Feedback	Ongoing assessments tracked progress, identified challenges, and allowed real-time adjustments to enhance student engagement and learning. Participants were encouraged to share any comments they might have with the organisers and instructors of the BIP course.
9	Valid, Reliable, and Transparent Assessment	Assessment criteria for passing the course were clearly communicated, ensuring fair and structured evaluation of course outputs.
10	Effective and Timely Feedback	Regular feedback was provided throughout the pilot, helping students track their progress, reflect critically, and refine their learning strategies. Instructors also provided open feedback on participants' work.

2.1.6 Key outcomes

2.1.6.1 ECTS harmonization

Out of a total of 33 participants who started the course and joined the online modules, 28 successfully completed the BIP course and earned the ECTS certification, formally recognising their achievements and encouraging active participation throughout the programme. To ensure formal recognition of the course, ECTS credits were awarded through an existing module at UNIZA's Faculty of Operation and Economics of Transport and Communications, titled *"Transport Planning and Sustainable Mobility."* This process required close collaboration with study programme guarantors and faculty instructors from the very beginning.

Figure 9: Completion of the course and ECTS certificates at the UNIZA pilot

2.1.6.2 Solutions developed for urban challenges

A major outcome of the course was the development of innovative, practical solutions for two real-world case studies.

- **Safe and sustainable school access (Case Study 1):** Students proposed a diverse set of targeted interventions to improve safety and reduce car dependency near schools. These included traffic-calming measures, dedicated pedestrian and child-friendly infrastructure, and safe drop-off zones that work within the existing road layout. One immediate, low-cost suggestion, repurposing existing parking bays for school drop-offs during peak hours (7:00–8:00 am), was swiftly adopted by the city.
- **Intelligent transport solutions (Case Study 2):** For the second case study, students designed smart traffic management systems using digital tools and real-time data, proposed enhanced multimodal connectivity to better integrate walking, cycling, and public transport, and suggested design strategies to minimise pedestrian–vehicle conflicts, particularly in high-traffic areas.

Figure 10: Presentation of suggested solutions to local authority at the UNIZA pilot

A selection of student assignments from the UNIZA BIP pilot is presented in Appendix A: UNIZA BIP pilot student assignments.

2.1.6.3 Feedback from local authorities

The Department of the Chief Architect of the City of Žilina (UHA) provided written feedback on the students' traffic calming proposals for **Case Study 1**, highlighting feasibility, regulatory constraints, and areas for further development.

Traffic Calming & Pedestrian Safety: Narrowing roads before pedestrian crossings was seen as a strong idea, with potential to replace existing horizontal markings with more visible alternatives. However, placing deceleration cushions before crossings is restricted by traffic regulations, though they could be used in inner-block streets. Parking spaces near crossings should ideally be relocated to prevent children from crossing traffic when exiting vehicles. The “Kiss and Ride” proposal aligned well with the city's urban study, but limitations such as high green areas and road width constraints must be considered.

Cycling Infrastructure: Students' cycle path proposals were well connected to existing routes, but new cycle lanes must adhere to width regulations. The planned change in cycle path colour from green to red must also be accounted for. Some roads are too narrow for safe cycling, and driver behaviour remains a challenge, but widening bike lanes and adding

protective zones could improve safety. Although shared zones for cyclists, pedestrians, and cars exist in neighbouring countries, their implementation in Slovakia remains a future challenge due to financial constraints.

Public Transport & Education: Encouraging active mobility through educational sessions for students and parents was praised as an effective approach. Public transport improvements were identified as essential, with the city already preparing school campaigns to promote better public spaces and mobility solutions.

The feedback emphasised aligning student proposals with urban plans, verifying feasibility with traffic engineers, and considering financial and regulatory constraints while aiming for innovative yet practical solutions.

The solutions proposed by students for **Case Study 2**, which focused on the vehicle access restriction zone, were discussed in detail during their presentation with the local authority. This verbal exchange allowed students to receive immediate feedback, clarify any uncertainties, and explore the feasibility of their ideas within the city's regulatory and infrastructural constraints. The discussion provided valuable insights into practical implementation challenges and helped students refine their solutions to better align with real-world urban planning considerations.

All feedback was openly discussed among students, course instructors, and the local authority, fostering a collaborative learning environment. Engaging in direct dialogue allowed students to refine their proposals, gain deeper insights into real-world constraints, and develop more practical, well-informed solutions.

2.2 Pilot at ISCTE in Portugal

2.2.1 Motivation

The ISCTE pilot course entitled **Cities Futures - Interdisciplinary Challenges** took place within the broader theme of **Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient Cities** of the European InCITIES project. This pilot course was implemented as an Erasmus+ BIP focused on the **Interdisciplinary Challenges** related to Cities Futures and their integration with the thematic areas identified in the InCITIES Work Package on Research (WP2), in order to develop future consciousness and agency for building the future of cities. Concrete and authentic real-life challenges proposed by the InCITIES Associated Partners (APs) *CP - Comboios de Portugal*, *Wegenblocks* and *Inovar Autismo*, in a bottom-up implementation approach, were the building blocks of the ISCTE pilot course, through the implementation of the Learning by Developing (LbD) pedagogical model.

The BIP implemented the ISCTE Pilot course task, framed by the InCITIES work package on Capacity Building Actions on Learning by Developing Pedagogical Model in Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient Cities (WP6). This pilot course, organised by ISCTE, open to all InCITIES partners and to the PIONEER network, aimed at developing an innovative perspective on the future of cities based on the principles and pedagogical practices of LbD, involving from the outset the APs of the project directly linked to the Lisbon Metropolitan Area.

There are many challenges that the Lisbon Metropolitan Area, like any other international city, is facing and from which it can benefit from the development of this project and, in particular, from the implementation of this pilot course on ***Cities Futures - Interdisciplinary Challenges***.

With a focus on the disciplinary area of *Information Sciences and Technologies*, this BIP pilot course dealt with complex and interdisciplinary issues, which is to think about the future of cities with a bottom-up approach, based on the challenges proposed by the APs, and therefore calls on other related skills such as *informatics, data science and visualisation, information systems, architecture, sociology, urban studies and mobility, public policy and marketing*, as related fields.

This interdisciplinary approach aimed to equip participants with the knowledge to address the proposed challenges. Moreover, the participants engaged in collaborative teamwork exercises, framed by the LbD pedagogical model, culminating in presentations delivered

during the on-site component of the programme hosted in Lisbon. In that regard, ISCTE promoted a *Hackathon* during the last day of the onsite BIP pilot course, to help engage the learners. The Hackathon was entitled: ***Future Cities from Vivid Reality: Inclusive and Sustainable and Challenges in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area.***

2.2.2 Main objectives

This pilot was implemented as an Erasmus+ BIP pilot and part of the European Project InCITIES, led by ISCTE, aimed to support the development of interdisciplinary and innovative perspectives for thinking about the cities of the future, within the global challenges of Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient Cities.

Participants were expected to carry out a set of authentic and real tasks according to the challenges proposed by the InCITIES APs. Based on the reality of each AP, the challenges are designed and linked to specific themes and must be tackled by the course participants in working group project mode.

The course has the following objectives:

1. Designing and developing solutions to the concrete problems resulting from the challenges proposed by the APs', discussing the solutions with the lecturers and representatives of the APs, while applying the LbD pedagogical model. The discussion with the APs' representatives took place at 3 different sessions (initial, intermediate and final during the Hackathon).
2. Iteration and improvement of the proposed solutions and presentation of the solutions at a final Hackathon event, evaluated by a mixed jury made up of 12 members, combining lecturers and representatives of the APs.
3. Increasing the social relations and communication skills, enriching the proposal solutions by the multiculturalism of the participants.

2.2.3 Teaching methods

The short course applied various teaching methods, including lectures, debates, collaborative activities, experiential learning through to site visits related to the challenges and group work based on the LbD pedagogical model. The students were the main actors in solving the challenges proposed by the APs, analysing the problems and developing solutions as a group.

The integration of interdisciplinary approaches enriches their understanding of the problems, emerging trends and the feasibility of the solutions they propose. Emphasising active participation and critical thinking, the course applies theoretical knowledge to real-world scenarios, reflecting its focus on problem-solving.

The LbD approach encouraged practical workshop-style learning that is challenge-based, engaging, active, bottom-up, with the involvement of APs, lecturers and tutors. Students took part in student group collaborative work, culminating in presentations delivered during the face-to-face component of the programme in Lisbon. ISCTE promotes the Hackathon during the face-to-face component of the BIP pilot course held in Lisbon to help engage students and allow them to present their work to a jury.

2.2.4 Learning outcomes of the ISCTE pilot course

Technical competences:

- Learning Outcomes (LO) 1: **Acquire** skills in problematising and testing creative and informed solutions.
- LO2: **Apply** user-centred data analysis.
- LO3: **Create** clear and accessible presentations and data visualisation support.
- LO4: **Formulate** clear presentation of the solutions for the challenges proposed by the APs.

Interpersonal skills:

- LO5: **Develop** international multidisciplinary LbD experience, teamwork and respect for colleagues' opinions.
- LO6: **Co-construct** solutions based on critical thinking, creative problem-solving, collaboration, critical observation, negotiation, and collaborative decision-making.
- LO7: **Apply** strategies to propose thoughtful solutions, autonomous work based on research into solutions and sustained construction of arguments.
- LO8: **Develop** oral and written communication skills and technical discussion skills.

2.2.5 Syllabus

The titles of the programme contents were the following:

- Programme Content (PC) 1. Learning by Developing for students

-
- PC2. Futurism – cities foresight
 - PC3. Information, data visualisation, and accessibility for user decision-making
 - PC4. Design thinking for envisioning cities futures with a focus on inclusive social design
 - PC5. Sensing mobility data
 - PC6. Transport innovation – sustainable urban development
 - PC7. Human-centred artificial intelligence

2.2.6 Coherence of the syllabus with the learning outcomes

All the programme contents (PC1 to PC7) are linked to the learning outcomes, both those relating to the acquisition of technical skills (LO1 to LO4) and those relating to the development of interpersonal skills (LO5 to LO8).

The PC is designed to ensure that students develop a comprehensive and interdisciplinary understanding of the challenges and opportunities for the future of cities. By focusing on real life tasks, the programme ensures that students are well equipped to contribute to the proposal of solutions that contribute to the development of inclusive, sustainable and resilient cities, in the context of the challenges proposed by ecosystem partners (APs).

2.2.7 Teaching methodology at the ISCTE pilot course

This ISCTE BIP pilot course applied the LbD pedagogical model. As applied to this BIP it included various lectures and experiential and active learning through the APs proposed challenges and students' group work. The students were the main actors in solving the challenges proposed by the APs, analysing the problems and developing solutions in group of students. Each students' group addressed one APs' challenge.

The integration of interdisciplinary approaches enriched the students' understanding of the problems, emerging trends and the feasibility of the solutions they propose. Emphasizing active participation and critical thinking, the course applied theoretical knowledge to real-world scenarios, reflecting its focus on problem-solving.

The LbD approach encouraged students' practical workshop-style learning that is challenge based, engaging, active, bottom-up, with the involvement of APs, lecturers and tutors.

Students took part in group collaborative work, culminating in presentations to be delivered during the face-to-face component of the programme in Lisbon. ISCTE organised the

Hackathon *Future Cities from Vivid Reality: Inclusive and Sustainable and Challenges in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area* during the face-to-face component of the BIP course held in Lisbon to help engage students and allow them to present their work to a jury. The jury was composed of teachers, tutors and representatives of the APs, and they evaluated the solutions the students' groups present.

2.2.8 Coherence between the teaching methodology and the learning outcomes

The LbD approach inherently supports the learning outcomes of the course by emphasizing real-life challenges, fostering theoretical and practical application (LO1 to LO4), and promoting teamwork and interdisciplinary collaboration (LO5 to LO8).

The combination of online and on-site learning ensures that students gain both theoretical knowledge and practical experience. Online and onsite modules provide the necessary background on the various interdisciplinary areas, focus on hands-on collaborative challenge-based projects and team-based problem-solving activities.

Students' group work and the hackathon foster the development of interpersonal and social skills (LO5 to LO8), and the promotion of teamwork, discussion, and problem-solving in a multidisciplinary and international multicultural context. To prepare for the hackathon, students collaborate to develop innovative solutions, enhancing their ability to work in teams and communicate effectively, guided by tutors, that culminates in a presentation of solutions to stakeholders (APs) and teachers.

The teaching methodology of the BIP "Cities Futures – Interdisciplinary Challenges" was meticulously designed to ensure alignment with the learning outcomes. By integrating the LbD approach, a hybrid learning format, students' collaborative teamwork, and the use of digital technologies, the BIP effectively prepares students to tackle real-world challenges in future cities, in the context of the APs' challenges. This alignment ensures that students not only gain theoretical knowledge but also develop practical skills, critical and design thinking, and effective communication abilities essential for their academic, professional, and civic growth.

2.2.9 Assessment

The assessment prioritised student participation and the quality of their work throughout the course. The assessment criteria were the following:

- In-depth analysis of the challenges proposed by the APs,

-
- Critical analysis and synthesis of concepts,
 - Iterative development of intermediate and final solution proposals,
 - Active participation in the online and onsite classes, namely within the tutorial sessions in groups of students with the tutor,
 - Effective communication and defence of the final solutions of each student in front of the jury of the Hackathon *Future Cities from Vivid Reality: Inclusive and Sustainable Challenges in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area*,
 - Written problem-solving report by the students' group of the challenge analysis and the solution they propose.

An individual final grade on the scale 0-20 values was attributed that considers all the previous criteria.

2.2.10 Partners of the course

The course pilot involved four Universities – with students, teachers and tutors – and three Associated Partners of the project InCITIES, and also a student from a fifth university. These were:

- ISCTE – UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF LISBON: Organiser, involved 6 teachers, 5 tutors and close involvement of 3 Associated Partners (APs)
- LAUREA UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES: involved 2 teachers and 10 students
- UNIVERSITY OF ŽILINA: involved 1 teacher and 5 students
- UNIVERSITY OF GUSTAVE EIFFEL: involved 11 students
- SLOVAK UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY: 1 student
- Associated Partners (APs): CP - Comboios de Portugal, Wegenblocks and Inovar Autismo

2.2.11 Dissemination of the ISCTE pilot course

The ISCTE BIP pilot course was dully disseminated using a flyer (Figure 11), social networks, emails and InCITIES website that highlights the course curriculum, the involved institutions, and the AP challenges.

Figure 11 – Flyer of the ISCTE Pilot

2.2.12 Students' participation

The BIP pilot course had the active participation of 27 students from 4 different institutions, 3 of which are from the InCITIES consortium, namely, Laurea, UNIZA and Université Gustave Eiffel (UGE) (Figure 12). In fact, the BIP only had one student from a HEI outside the consortium (coming from the Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava).

This student number and their HEI of origin can be explained, from one side, by the priority given to students from consortium partners and, from the other side, by the limit number of students that could be assigned to each AP challenges. Good practices of the LbD method

recommended a limited number of students per group (in this regard Laurea recommendations were to have groups between 4-6 elements maximum).

Figure 12 - Distribution of students HEI of origin at the ISCTE pilot

Figure 13 - Distribution of the student's nationalities at the ISCTE pilot

Figure 14 - Distribution of the student's nationalities 2 at the ISCTE pilot

Wider range was observed in terms of students nationally. As presented in Figure 13 and Figure 14, there was a good diversity in this regard, with more emphasis on French, Finnish and Slovak students, as expected. This diversity was also observed in the student's field of study, that ranged from Business Administration, Urban Planning, Languages, Management, Social Services and Health Care Management, Information and Network Technologies, etc. Regarding the cycle of study, the large majority were from Bachelor degree (~78%), being 22% from MSc level (Figure 15). Worth mentioning the large participation of woman in the BIP pilot course, as they represent more than 3/4 of the total student participants (Figure 16). Also noteworthy, the age distribution, as more than 1/3 of the participants had ages above 25 (Figure 17). This large spectrum enriched each of the working groups and, consequently, the final works.

Figure 15 - Distribution of the student's cycle at the ISCTE pilot

Figure 16 - Distribution of the student's gender at the ISCTE pilot

Figure 17 - Distribution of the student's age at the ISCTE pilot

2.2.13 Implementation of the ISCTE pilot

2.2.13.1 Online sessions schedule

Usually, the online sessions were organised as follow:

Teacher presentation of around 1h to 1h30 (adapted by the teacher according to the needs of the module), followed by 15 to 30 min of Q&A, and then 30 min with the tutors of each group within Zoom breakout rooms.

All online speakers' sessions on Wednesday started at 11h30 am – 13h30 pm CET (10h30 am - 12h30 pm Lisbon, 12h30 - 14h30 Helsinki), except the session of the 4th of December 2024 that starts one hour earlier, at 10h30 am -12h30 pm CET (9h30 am - 11h30 Lisbon, 11h30 – 13h30 Helsinki).

The sessions of the groups G1 to G3 with the tutors took place on Wednesday, just after the speakers' sessions. The sessions of the groups G4 and G5 took place on Thursdays at 3 pm CET (4 pm Helsinki) for group G4 and at 4 pm CET (5 pm Helsinki) for group G5.

2.2.13.2 Online Lectures

The online component of ISCTE BIP course Cities Futures - Interdisciplinary Challenges was developed in nine moments, as presented in Table 4. This component had the active

participation of several professors from the three InCITIES institutions, namely: Elina Wainio and Sanna Ketonen-Oksi from Laurea, Yannick Cornet from UNIZA and Catarina Ferreira da Silva, Maria do Carmo Botelho, Miguel Sales Dias, Sérgio Moro, Isabel Alexandre from Iscte. Figure 18 presents some snapshots of some of the abovementioned online lectures.

Table 4: Agenda of the online lectures of the ISCTE Pilot

DAY	TIME	LECTURE
Wednesday, 30 Oct. 24	11:30 CET to 13:30 CET	Inaugural Session Welcome by ISCTE; Presentation of the BIP components LbD for students; Q&A discussion ISCTE (Catarina Ferreira da Silva, tutors), LAUREA (Elina Wainio)
Wednesday, 06 Nov. 24	11:30 CET to 13:30 CET	Presentation of the Hackathon challenges Q&A Students' group sessions with tutors ISCTE (moderator, tutors), Associated Partners representatives
Wednesday, 13 Nov. 24	11:30 CET to 13:30 CET	Futurism - cities foresight Q&A Students' group sessions with tutors LAUREA (Sanna Ketonen-Oksi), ISCTE (moderator, tutors)
Wednesday, 20 Nov. 24	11:30 CET to 13:30 CET	Information, Data Visualisation and Accessibility for User Decision Making Q&A Students' group sessions with tutors ISCTE (Maria do Carmo Botelho, tutors)
Wednesday, 27 Nov. 24	11:30 CET to 13:30 CET	Design thinking for envisioning cities futures focused on the LbD challenges Q&A Students' group sessions with tutors ISCTE (Miguel Sales Dias, moderator, ISCTE transversal skills lab facilitator, tutors)
Wednesday, 4 Dez. 24	10:30 CET to 12:30 CET	Sensing mobility data Q&A Students' group sessions with tutors ISCTE (Sérgio Moro, moderator, tutors)

Wednesday, 11 Dez. 24 11:30 CET to 13:30 CET **Transport innovation - Sustainable Urban Development**
 Q&A
 Students' group sessions with tutors
 UNIZA (Yannick Cornet), ISCTE (moderator, tutors)

Wednesday, 18 Dez. 24 11:30 CET to 13:30 CET **Intermediate presentations to the associated partners**
 Q&A
 Students' group sessions with tutors
 ISCTE (moderator, teachers, tutors), APs' representatives

Wednesday, 15 Jan. 25 11:30 CET to 13:30 CET **Human centred Artificial Intelligence**
 Q&A
 Students' group sessions with tutors
 ISCTE (Isabel Alexandre, moderator, tutors)

Figure 18 – Snapshots from different online lectures at the ISCTE pilot

2.2.13.3 On-site activities

The in-person component included:

1. **Academic seminars** by prof. Luís Coelho, Politécnico de Setúbal (IPS), focusing on the Inclusive Social Design & sister EU project – E3UDRES2 Ent-r-e-novators.
2. **Presentations of concrete experiences** by sector actors in Portugal, both at public level and NGO's. Cristina Alves Pereira (CML) and Gilmário Duarte (Inovar Autismo) participated in the *Lisbon Round table on future cities thinking*. Students had the opportunity to visit two InCITIES associated partners namely: to Inovar Autismo (in Setúbal), and to CLM (Civil Protection Command Centre in Lisbon).
3. **Applied exercise** on the challenges proposed by the InCITIES Associated partners with the supervision of ISCTE tutors, and co-supervision of ISCTE teachers, LbD experts (Elina Wainio and Sanna Ketonen-Oksi from Laurea) and UNIZA Pilot co-coordinator (Yannick Cornet).

In Table 5 is presented the agenda of the *in-person* lectures of the ISCTE BIP pilot Cities Futures - Interdisciplinary Challenges.

Table 5: Agenda of the on-site lectures of the ISCTE Pilot

DAY	TIME	LECTURE	Location
Monday, 20 Jan. 25	15:00 CET to	Welcome Session! Orientation @ISCTE Maria das Dores Guerreiro, Vice-Rector for the Internationalization at Iscte, Catarina Ferreira da Silva, Department of Information Science and Technology (ISTA) at Iscte, Tomás Nascimento, president of ISCTE Student Association	ISCTE, Building 4
	17:00 CET		Auditorium A306
Tuesday, 21 Jan. 25	10:00 CET	Workshop Session with students – Working with Tutors ISCTE Tutors	ISCTE, Building 2 B2.01 (G5); B2.02 (G1); C2.01 (G2); C2.02 (G3); C2.05 (G3)
	11:30 CET	Coffee Break	
	12:00 CET	Lisbon Round table on future cities thinking with Associated Partners Inovar Autismo and Lisbon Municipality (CML) Catarina Ferreira da Silva, ISCTE (moderator), Cristina Alves Pereira (CML), Gilmário Duarte (InovarAutismo)	ISCTE, Building 1 Auditorium ONE01 Paquete de Oliveira
	13:30 CET	Lunch	
	15:00 CET	Visit Associated partner – InovarAutismo (in Setúbal)	Private Bus
	Wednesday 22 Jan. 25	10:00 CET	Workshop Session with students – Working with Tutors ISCTE Tutors
11:30 CET		Coffee Break	
12:00 CET		Inclusive Social Design & project – E3UDRES2 Ent-r-e-novators Catarina Ferreira da Silva, ISCTE (moderator), Luís Coelho, Politécnico de Setúbal (IPS)	ISCTE, Building 1 Auditorium ONE01 Paquete de Oliveira

	13:30 CET	Lunch	
	15:00 CET	Tech Innovation and entrepreneurship / visit AUDAX-ISCTE tech. transfer unit	ISCTE Lisbon Campus
	16:00 CET to 18:00 CET	Guided bus tour – Lisbon Heritage sites	Private Bus
Thursday, 24 Jan. 25	10:00 CET	Workshop Session with students – Working with Tutors <i>ISCTE Tutors</i>	ISCTE, Building 2 B2.01 (G5); B2.02 (G1); C2.01 (G2); C2.02 (G3); C2.05 (G3)
	11:30 CET	Coffee Break	
	12:00 CET	Workshop Session with students – Working with Tutors <i>ISCTE Tutors</i>	ISCTE, Building 2 B2.01 (G5); B2.02 (G1); C2.01 (G2); C2.02 (G3); C2.05 (G3)
	13:30 CET	Lunch	
	15:00 CET	Visit Associated Partner CML – Civil Protection Command Centre (Monsanto, Lisbon)	Private Bus
Friday, 25 Jan. 25	10:00 CET	Hackathon presentations & Jury Contest Final Decisions <i>Catarina Ferreira da Silva, ISCTE (moderator), ISCTE Teachers and Tutors, APs representatives</i>	ISCTE, Building 1 Auditorium ONE01 Paquete de Oliveira
	11:30 CET	Coffee Break	
	12:00 CET	Wrap-up and Farewell	

Below, in photos 1 to 2, one may observe some snapshots of the on-site activities in Lisbon – January 2025.

Photo 3 - Group photo of all BIP participants during the BIP pilot welcome session with the presence of the ISCTE vice-rector for the Internacionalization Maria das Dores Guerreiro

Photo 4 – Photo during the Round table on future cities thinking with the Associated Partners Inovar Autismo and Lisbon Municipality (CML)

Photo 5 – Photo during the visit to Inovar Autismo

Photo 6 – Photo during the Inclusive Social Design & EU sister project – E3UDRES2 Ent-r-e-novators session with professor Luís Coelho from Politécnico of Setúbal

Photo 7 – Photo during the Visit Associated Partner CML – Civil Protection Command Centre (Monsanto, Lisbon)

Photo 8 – Opening session of the Hackathon by the ISCTE Vice-Rector for the PIONEER Alliance Helena Carreiras

Photo 9 – Hackathon presentations with the presence of the AP representatives, teachers and tutors

Photo 10 – Wining group of the Hackathon with the representative of CP – Comboios de Portugal (Hackathon sponsor)

2.2.14 ECTS Harmonization

All students' participants ISCTE pilot course successfully completed the BIP pilot course and earned the ECTS certification, formally recognising their achievements and encouraging active participation throughout the programme.

3 Conclusion

Through these educational innovations, the UNIZA BIP pilot effectively showcased how the LbD pedagogical model can enhance sustainable mobility education by offering students interdisciplinary, hands-on, and meaningful learning experiences. The pilot created a dynamic environment that blended innovation, collaboration, and real-world application.

The insights gained provide a valuable foundation for adapting the LbD model in future transport education initiative, both at UNIZA and at other institutions aiming to embed stakeholder-driven, practical learning into their curricula.

The ISCTE Pilot followed the same principles of the UNIZA pilot, regarding the LbD implementation, the combination of online learning with on-site activities and the active participation of local InCITIES Associated Partners stakeholders (national and private companies, NGO's and municipalities). The Associated Partners proposed challenges were completely aligned with ISR city themes and were enthusiastically addressed by the different student groups. The implementation of a Hackathon, in the last day of the onsite week, was an opportunity to involve all the BIP participants, e.g., students, associated partner representatives, professors and tutors, in a single event.

Although implementing the LbD model demands careful coordination, particularly in areas such as credit recognition, funding, stakeholder involvement, and course logistics, the key driver is a shift in mindset: moving away from traditional, top-down instruction toward a more coaching-oriented, student-empowered approach that positions learners as active participants in the educational process.

Appendix A: UNIZA BIP pilot student assignments, ISCTE BIP Pilot AP challenges and example of one group work

Suggestions for mitigation of air pollution in Zilina

Air pollution sources

IMPROVE PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION SYSTEM

1

Allocate a **bus that passes through most of the city and goes to both schools**, during rush hour

2

Invest in **electric** buses, and charging stations for electric cars

3

Priority lanes for public transportation, making them more important around the city

4

Share cars
Walk if possible

PROMOTE BIKE-SHARING SERVICES

1

Create proper **infrastructures**,
as suggested last modules

3

Create a system of **interconnectivity**
between methods of transportation (close to
a bus stop, there is a bike-sharing station)

2

Not only contributes to **reduce the individual
carbon footprint**, but also promotes **physical
wellbeing**

TRAFFIC CALMING SCENARIOS

1

speed bumps to reduce speed
of cars

2

This would reduce the emissions
from car transport, that is, the
emissions of PM

GREEN SPACES AND AWARENESS

1

Green spaces along roads absorb harmful pollutants emitted by vehicles and improve air quality in urban areas

2

Setting up air quality monitoring stations across the city to track changes in pollution levels-
awareness

3

Involve the community in the benefits of green spaces to raise awareness, but also to foster a sense of **responsibility** for the preservation and maintenance to improve air quality and health in the long term

GREEN SPACES AND AWARENESS

1

**save water with automatic
irrigation**

3

**green infrastructure with
green roofs, eco-bridges**

2

Avoid heat islands inside the city

Characteristics of surrounding environment

Levels of PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂ and SO₂ are usually between 20 and 40, indicating relatively moderate levels of air pollution

CO levels are significantly higher, often exceeding 140

- This disparity suggests a potential cause for concern, as high levels of CO can pose direct health risks.
- While PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂ and SO₂ are associated with various sources such as vehicle emissions, industrial processes and combustion, excessively high levels of CO may indicate specific localised sources such as heavy traffic congestion.

THANK YOU!

Group 4

HOW TO REDUCE VULNERABILITY IN THE CITY?

Martinska School

Focus

Heat Waves

Droughts

Flash Floods

Gray measures (infrastructure)

Blue-green measures (ecosystem)

Soft measures (policy, legal, social, financial)

Windows (Heat Wave / Gray)

Replace these current windows of wood and with one pane

by new windows (PVC or Aluminium) with double-glazed panes

Either with reflecting glass film or blinds.

Roof Greening (Heat Wave, Flash Flood / Gray, Blue - Green)

Currently: Flat roofs with dark covering and low water absorption

Cooling indoor and better air quality outside in the surrounding area

Much higher water absorption

Afforestation (Flash Flood / Drought, blue-green)

Each class that starts school plants a tree and flowers in an area near the river, which they look after in the following years of primary school (become a kind of ritual)

Forests are regulating water flow and water resources through their hydrological-related ecosystem services and can act as carbon sink

Heat wave awareness and action plan (Soft)

Education and awareness programs

- **Workshops or seminars to educate students, staff and parents:** risks associated with heat waves and counter-measures (e.g. staying hydrated, sunscreen)

Heat wave action plan

- Development of a **plan outlining the steps that should be taken**, in case a temperature threshold is met;
 - Restrict sun exposure, ensure water and sunscreen availability;

Thank you for your attention!

UNDERSTANDING AND ASSESSING VULNERABILITY

Group 1

Flooding & extreme temperature

Grey measures

- Porous paving (parking area)**
- Absorb water
 - Decrease possibility of flooding
 - Traffic calming measure
 - clear separation with traffic lane

Extreme Temperature

Blue-Green Measures

- **Green schoolyards and outdoor learning space**
 - Increase natural shade
 - Cooling effects, decrease temperature
 - Create comfortable outdoor environment during heatwave
 - Improve mental health, cognitive function, and overall well-being
 - Provide community hubs outside school hours

- **Water drinking fountain**
 - Avoid dehydration
 - In public area: park, bus stop, school
- **Fountain**
 - Stimulate evaporation, decrease air temperature
 - Improve public space attractiveness

Extreme Temperature

Soft Measures

01

Prioritised target groups:

- Students
- Elderly

02

Actions:

- Warning announcement about upcoming heatwave
- Education programme about how to be cautious during heatwave

Throughout a **HEATWAVE**, keep yourself cool and hydrated

Drink water regularly.

Avoid alcohol and too much caffeine and sugar

Eat small meals and eat more often

Wear light, loose-fitting clothes

Wear a hat or cap and sunglasses.

Take cool showers or baths

 World Health Organization

CYCLING IN ŽILINA: GARAZDA AND MARTINSKA

Group 4.

UNIVERSITY
OF ŽILINA

OFFERED NEW BIKE LANES

➤ new offered bike lanes are in red lines

➤ installation of special road signs for bicycles on all roads;

➤ The width of all bicycle paths should not be less than the international standard

legend

- bikesharing station
- cycletrack/lane
- highway_cycleway

Search Google Maps

11 Černovská

Žilina, Žilina Region

Google Street View

Jun 2022

[See more dates](#)

Google

Černovská street

Search Google Maps

Žilina, Žilina Region

Google Street View

Jun 2014

See more dates

Google

Matice Slovenskej

24 m width ▾ 57,000 people/hr Zilina, Slovakia

Group 4

Primary School Martinska

1. Draw the traffic calming measures you propose onto the map of the neighborhood.

- Kiss & Drive Lane on blank space in front of school
- Lower down speed limit to 30
- Renew existing crosswalks
- Increase number of crosswalks
- Speed bumps
- Parking space for teacher behind the school to not disturb Kiss & Drive Lane

2. Design a plan to improve visibility and safety at crosswalks in school zones.

1. Renew crosswalk surface and signage, and improve pedestrian visibility

2. Restructure road in a user focused approach

3. Add speed reduction devices, before crosswalks and in long straightaways

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1. Renew crosswalk surface and signage, and improve pedestrian visibility

2. Restructure road in a user focused approach

3. Add speed reduction devices, before crosswalks and in long straightaways

3. Assess the accessibility of schools for students with disabilities and recommend enhancements.

PROBLEMS

- Missing marking on sidewalks (and crossings)
- Missing connection between pavements
- Actual entrance without any adjustment for disabled students

3. Assess the accessibility of schools for students with disabilities and recommend enhancements.

SOLUTIONS

- Tactile sidewalks and crossings
- Height differences between road and sidewalk
- Dividing island between road and sidewalk
- Barrier-free entrance

4. Investigate the role of public transportation in providing safe school access and propose optimizations.

- Survey implies that public transport only plays a subordinate role
- Unused potentials
- Public transport must be made more attractive → purposely preferred to alternative modes of transportation

4. Investigate the role of public transportation in providing safe school access and propose optimizations.

Advantages and potential of public transport for safe school access

- Important for students who do not have access to private transportation or live too far away to walk or bike to school
- Avoid the risks associated with walking or biking longer distances, e.g. crossing dangerous roads
- Comfortable transport for students in bad weather conditions
- Pooling of larger groups of people -> traffic intensity and pollution can be reduced

Strategies and optimization opportunities

- Increased frequency and reliability of public transportation services → students need to be on time in class
- Safe and accessible bus stops and stations, with sufficient lighting, seating, and shelter from the weather
- Implementation of dedicated school bus services or routes specifically for students
- Education and awareness programs to promote safe behavior when using public transport (waiting in designated areas, respect for other passengers, etc.)

5.Design a ‘Safe Routes to School’ program tailored to a local school’s needs

Safe Routes To School Program – summarize all of the previous answers

Design in 2 steps:

1.Collection of all necessary information for the program:

- Location of the school;
- Accessibility;
- Data extrat from a survey (the survey must contain the ages of the children, means of transport used, most attended school hours);
- Cooperation with parents (to identify specific safety problems the children face).

2.Program Plan:

- Infrastructure improvements;
- Educational initiatives;
- Enforcement

(explained in the next slide)

5. Design a 'Safe Routes to School' program tailored to a local school's needs

Program Plan:

Home Assignment 4

Group 1

Claudia Herrera Quintero

Leonor de Brito

Doston Nurullaev

Fabian Fehr

Valeriia Zelinová

Irene Sitohang

Teresa Real Byrne

Lourenço Ribeiro

Ulugbek Yusupov

01

Case Study
Gorazda

Groups of interest

- Students
- People living around the school area
- Teachers and instructors

Location context

- Nearby School
- Limited Access
- Limited Space

Bike friendly infrastructure

- Connect missing link of existing cycle track/lane
- Add bike sharing station near school / residential complex
- Apply bicycle street on road around school → suitable for limited space

example:

- Legend
- existing bike sharing station
 - existing cycle track/lane
 - new bike sharing station

02

Case Study

Martinská

Groups of interest

- Students
- People living around the school area
- Teachers and instructors

Location context

- Challenge street space
- Many options
- High traffic

Bike friendly infrastructure

- Connect missing link of existing cycle track/lane
- Add bike sharing station near school / residential complex
- Add bicycle lane and road markings on road around school

example:

- Legend
- existing bike sharing station
 - existing cycle track/lane
 - new bike sharing station

03

**Measures to
enhance the level
of cycling**

01

Organize cycling events, competitions, and community rides to promote cycling culture and encourage more people to take up cycling as a recreational activity or mode of transportation.

02

Repaint road markings to allow shared use of the road by cars and bicycles, with accessible bike lanes for cars.

03

Encourage workplaces to provide facilities like bike storage, showers, and changing rooms for cyclists, and offer incentives for employees who cycle to work.

04

Offer **incentives** such as subsidies for purchasing bicycles, tax breaks for cycling-related expenses, or rewards for commuting by bike.

Thanks!

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Traffic calming measures

Case study: primary and nursery school of Saint Gorazda

Group 1

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Lourenço Ribeiro

Teresa Real Byrne

Ulugbek Yusupov

Valeriia Zelinová

Questions

Question 1

Draw the traffic calming measures you propose onto the map of the neighborhood.

Question 2

Design a plan to improve visibility and safety at crosswalks in school zones.

Question 3

Assess the accessibility of schools for students with disabilities and recommend enhancements.

Question 4

Investigate the role of public transportation in providing safe school access and propose optimizations.

Question 5

Design a 'Safe Routes to School' program tailored to a local school's needs.

Road users

- Motorised vehicles exiting from road E50
- Motorised vehicles from all other directions
- Trolleybus
- Pedestrians
- Cyclists

Objective

- Students cross safely at treatment area
- Traffic calming implementation
 - Suitable for trolley bus

General measures

- Narrow road near pedestrian crossings
- Speed limit 30 km/h in marked area
- Speed cushions as needed near crossings
- Marking for parking spots (line to separate from road)
- Suggest other color for cycle lane, e.g., green
- Widen cycle lane (will be decided by road planner)

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Locations for 30 km/h signs and speed monitors

- 30 km/h sign
- Speed monitor
- Bus/trolleybus stop
- Pedestrian crossing

Solution

- Extended green area
- On-street parking
- Zebra cross
- Road asphalt
- Cycle lane
- Green area

A - before

- One lane road
- On-street parking

A - after

B - before

- Cycle lane available
- Wide pedestrian crossing

B - after

Maintain some parking spots

- Maintain and widen cycle lane
- Pavement in green

Narrower road to cross = increased safety

C - before

C - after

- Widen median
- Eliminate several parking spots
- Add speed cushion

End of on-street parking

Maintain some parking spots

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Solution for students with disabilities: kiss and ride

Example: kiss and ride in France

Questions

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Role of Public Transportation

**Reduces traffic
congestion**

Safe space

**Less time wasted
and opportunity to
socialize**

**Less air and noise
pollution**

Questions

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'Safe Routes to School'

Option A

Car Travel

Option B

Public Transport

Option C

Group

- Partner with local navigation apps to highlight safer and more efficient routes for parents to take students to school.
- Implement safe drop-off and pick-up zones at the school, with designated and supervised areas for student arrival and departure.
- Conduct awareness campaigns for parents on the importance of following traffic rules and practicing defensive driving when transporting children to school.

'Safe Routes to School'

Option A

Car Travel

Option B

Public Transport

Option C

Group

- Negotiate with local public transport authorities to improve bus routes and schedules serving the school area, ensuring accessible and safe options for students.
- Promote the use of public transportation among students by offering discounted transport cards or special passes for students.
- Conduct educational sessions for students on how to use public transportation safely, including how to read bus maps, proper behavior at bus stops, and respect for other passengers.

'Safe Routes to School'

Option A

Car Travel

Option B

Public Transport

Option C

Group

- Organize supervised "group walking" programs where students can meet and walk together to school, promoting neighborhood safety and a sense of community.
- Establish safe meeting points around the school area where students can gather and start walking together.
- Create a "buddy system" where students are paired up to walk together, promoting responsibility and safety among peers.

 genesis.studio

who we are

Founded in December 2018, **genesis.studio** is a professional consulting, development and integration services provider as well a software house.

Our company specializes in customized solutions to accelerate businesses, and we split these into three categories:

- **The first is centered in the Optimization of Processes** – We build, deploy and manage Robot Process Automations, GenAI implementations and Machine Learning Algorithms to emulate human interaction.
- **The second is focused on Outsourcing and Nearshore**, where we try to find the best profiles for our customers' opportunities, whether it is an isolated profile or the creation of an entire team;
- **The third area is dedicated to Digital Product Development**, typically covering end-to-end projects across various technologies, with a specialization in Machine Learning, Blockchain, Data Engineering and Automation.

our **gen.help**

genesis.studio was the first company in Portugal with an Azure GPT implementation going live for the Portuguese Ministry of Justice. This was also the first implementation of Azure GPT in any European Public Administration.

This marked the beginning of numerous projects that gave us proven experience and establishing us as a reliable partner for many clients.

gen.help is a platform that allows the creation of virtual assistants, based on the GPT algorithm. It is agnostic to the use case, helping businesses and people embrace the power of GenAI in a cost-effective way, while reducing operational costs.

gen.help may be applied to different departments, such as HR, IT, Finance, Customer Support, Procurement, Suppliers, Partners, etc.

what we offer

Drive Digital Transformation

We help clients accelerate their business and operations using the latest cutting-edge technology, covering the whole lifecycle.

Automate Digital Processes

We develop solutions that automate your business processes, activities and tasks using robots, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence.

Outsourcing and Nearshore

We are committed to find the best professionals while also focusing on active communication and building a long-term commitment.

Design Products and Experiences

We focus on full product immersion, combining your vision with market research and applying state of the art technology, creating a tailor-made solution.

Extract Value from Data

We turn data into insights and create multiple behavior predictions based on historical analysis so that your business can discover opportunities.

reference projects: DLT

We have profiled and engaged with over 300 institutions in Europe, the Middle East, Africa and Asia, and explored and advised on the applicability of blockchain/DLT for uses cases in banking, payments, insurance, government and public administration, telecom, health, supply chain, logistics and transportation.

Consulting & Advisory

European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA): mapping requirements and architecting a decentralized maritime data exchange network and extending the SafeSeaNet platform with blockchain/DLT

Development

- Smartshare – Legal Data Sharing Agreements;
- Development of Plano-A using Hyperledger fabric;
- 1st integration of Liferay with DAML, for Insurance policy and claim management;
- 1st integration of Liferay with Hyperledger Indy, for self-sovereign Digital Identity;
- PoC for Supply Chain & Logistics-oriented Track & Trace, using Hyperledger Fabric and Liferay.

reference projects: automation

We have clients from different sectors, such as retail, drink and ice-cream production, recruitment, health, banking and energy.

Retail clients

Case 1: Automation of Smart Reporting to work data, transferring it between platforms and areas of the company, creating statistics, alarms and smart data that allow a faster and more correct human analysis.

Case 2: Purchase order automation - creation of intelligent flows that can analyze a need and proceed with the purchase from a supplier. Ability to analyze payment, delays and billing errors.

Industry client

Case 1: Automated employee entry process that can fill in required information, notify the various areas about the new employee and activate essential processes, such as creating health insurance, notifying project managers, creating access card, e-mail accounts, delivery of material necessary for work, etc.

Other clients

Case 1: Automatic process that can read and analyze invoices, transfer data and warn if there are errors, internal or external.

Case 2: Intelligent management of raw material resources, capable of predicting stock rupture in company processes and forecasting sales.

Recruitment client

Case 1: Recruitment process that analyzes job opportunities, reads CVs, looks for the best candidates and contacts them.

reference projects: data/ML/AI

We have clients from different sectors, such as retail, drink and ice-cream production, recruitment, health, banking and energy.

Healthcare client

Case 1: Automatic process that analyzes Complaints and prioritizes responses, being able to respond automatically or transfer to the responsible area.

Energy client

Case 1: Preventive maintenance, by images or sensors, of factory structures or transport networks.

Government

Case 1: Evolutionary maintenance of portals such as Social Security.

Recruitment client

Case 1: Analysis of social media, what is written about the company, in which cases one must respond to prevent bad reputation, measure client satisfaction.

Other clients

Case 1: Forecast - Ability to predict a company's short and long-term sales spikes and breaks for better management of resources and raw materials.

Bank & Insurance clients

Case 1: Intelligent credit scoring process that predicts a customer's ability to repay a loan, insurance or other banking product.

Case 2: Cross-Selling: Ability to predict what are the best products to sell to a customer, predicting the time and nature of the need.

Case 3: Performing an end-to-end Mainframe Migration to newer, open-source technologies.

App Oeiras Move

App Oeiras Move is a one stop shop app for mobility services in the city of Oeiras, one of the richest cities of Portugal.

Services include:

- Surface Parking;
- Underground Parking;
- Bike sharing;

App Oeiras Move

Services to be implemented:

- EV charging;
- Scooter renting;
- Taxis;
- TVDE;
- Etc.

App Oeiras Move

Although the goal is to be a mobility app, there is also a great will to provide different services to the population, namely through gamification and discounts for being a resident, among others.

One of the biggest challenges will be how to know your customer (KYC). What does this mean?

- What type of citizens use bikes?
- Where do they pick and leave the bikes?
- Where and how long are the trips?
- Where should there be new or more docking stations?
- What other services bike users, use?

App Oeiras Move

To achieve this, do we need more data?

Which data?

Is it public or not?

Can we gather it on the app or not?

Can we pay users to provide us more data? Run campaigns?

contacts

keep in touch

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Lisboa

!novarautismo.

A society for all

About us.

- Inovar Autismo is a national IPSS and NGO, **founded in December 2016**;
- The **basic concept** of our work is the construction of ‘A Society for All’, in which all people have a rightful place, independently of their disabilities or functionalities.

Methodological bases for our work:

- United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD)
- National Strategy for the Inclusion of People with Disabilities (ENIPD 2021-2025)
- European Strategy for the Rights of People with Disabilities (2021-2030)
- Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Our Methodology .

What the person
want to be/do

Focus on the
autistic person -
Person-centred
planning

Mediation /
Building skills in
the community

Focus on the
community

Empowering your child's autonomy and
self-determination

Focus on
the **family**

Inovar Team: CDI, Cavi,
PAs , Mediators/ Partners

Focus on the
Ecosystem and
working in
partnership

Our projects.

- Center for Innovation and Development for Inclusion (CIDI)
- Inclusion in the community;
- Inclusion in school contexts;
- Promoting access to employment;
- Developing competencies in the community and their structures for autism, human rights and inclusion;
- Training (autistic people, families, teachers, companies);
- Two centers for Independent Living (CAVI).

Inovar Autismo's CAVIs.

Inovar Autismo currently has two Independent Living Support Centres (**CAVI Alentejo** and **CAVI Setúbal**), with objective of:

1. Promoting independent living and autonomy for autistic people in the various contexts of the community and throughout the life cycle, through an integrated and holistic model.
2. To promote the self-determination, self-representation, human rights and social participation of the beneficiaries, as well as their quality of life and that of their families.
3. Train the community agents for the Social Model Disability.

Distinctive aspects of CAVIs:

1. Inovar Autismo's CAVIs are the **only ones** in the country to have provided, from the outset of their application, an action preferably dedicated **to autistic people**.
2. The beneficiaries are mostly young adults, so the work carried out is based on empowerment and the aim of **avoiding their institutionalization**.
3. The beneficiaries are of **both genders**, contradicting the idea that autism is only expressed in males.

Inclusion in School

The work of Inovar Autismo

2020

2021

2022

2023

2024

Inclusion at Work

The work of Inovar Autismo

inovarautismo.

Laboratório de Inovação & Emprego

Inclusão socioprofissional de jovens autistas
Capacitação de entidades empregadoras e estruturas de ensino

2023

Capacitar para o EMPREGO

inovarautismo.

INR Instituto Nacional de Reabilitação

2021

2019

2022

Inclusion in leisures activities

The work of Inovar Autismo

Autism & Sport

2023

2024

2019

2021

2022

2019

2021

CAVI Setúbal.

17 beneficiaries

1 woman and 16 men

Ages between 19y and 43y

17 Personal assistant

It cover 18 municipalities of
Lisbon Metropolitan Area

12 beneficiaries

3 women and 9 men

Ages between 17y and 45y

CAVI Alentejo.

10 Personal assistant

Évora district;
Beja district;
Portalegre district;
Santarém district.

Project's team.

Inês Ribeiro
Clinical Psychologist
Project Team
Coordinator

Anabela Carvalheira
Human Resources
Manager

Mariana Bico
Social and Organizational
Psychologist

Gilmaro Duarte
Psychology trainee

Bárbara Silva
Human Resources trainee

Cavi's technical team.

Catarina Pinto
CAVI Alentejo Coordinator

Rita Neves
CAVI Alentejo

Sara Aldeia
CAVI Setúbal
Coordinator

Michael Alencar
CAVI Setúbal

Challengers.

1. The existence Residence for Autonomy and Inclusion (RAI) is necessary
2. Difficulties in finding employment

1. Residence for Autonomy and Inclusion.

- The RAI is a temporary or permanent residential accommodation response, developed in a flat, villa or other similar type of housing, inserted in residential areas in the community.
- It is designed for people with disabilities, more than 18 years, who can/want to live independently.
- With individualized support, it provides the conditions for achieving their own goals autonomously and inclusively.
- It helps individuals to move out of family homes and lead more independent lives.

1. Residence for Autonomy and Inclusion.

- There are some RAIs in the country but few vacancies.
- An answer that remains elusive due to the current lack of resources and support.
- Low number (next to 5) people living together.

2. Difficulties in entering the labor .

Challenges

1. Difficulty in integrating into the labour market;
2. Difficulties with soft skills;
3. Difficulties in operationalization (building a CV, where to look for a job).

Our methodology

1. Person-centred planning
2. Soft skills training;
3. Systematic follow-up - CV creation, contacts with companies and interview support.

Inovar Autismo helps build CVs, prepare for interviews and establish contacts with companies;

2. Difficulties in entering the labor .

Challenges

1. Companies not able to include young people
2. Difficulties in including young people in work teams;
3. Recruitment based on quotas.

Our methodology

1. Training companies and the company team in terms of inclusion;
2. Structuring of timetables, tasks and face-to-face follow-up with young people and the team every two weeks;
3. Support with mediators and/or PAs.

Thank you!

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COMBOIOS DE PORTUGAL

Planeamento Estratégico

InCities

Trailblazing, Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient Cities

November 2024

COMBOIOS DE PORTUGAL

Contents:

1. PROPOSED CHALLENGES	3
A) CP LAB PROJECT	4

1. Proposed challenges

- a. The relationship between CP and IOT, and its ability to revolutionise the way information is presented and made available, focusing mainly on the following points:
 1. Placing the citizen at the centre of the information gathering and sharing process, considering the customer as a partner in the public service decision-making, taking into account their real needs;
 2. Breaking down European barriers to data collection/sharing/access.
- b. Strengthen and create knowledge interfaces, fostering open innovation and co-creation, as well as, making CP attractive to the labour market.

a) CP Lab Project

In order to frame the challenge of research and innovation in the field of training (HUBs) by implementing co-creation methods to develop a common research process, it is present the framework of the CP Lab project.

The CP Lab Project aims to be CP's key visibility, mobilisation and outreach initiative. It aims at co-creating, developing, testing and experimenting innovative solutions that solve the challenges of rail, promoting collaboration between start-ups, companies, academia and the community, and boosting technological and operational transformation to offer more efficient, sustainable and citizen-centred public transport.

In this respect, four channels have been identified that positively reinforce each other in the development and tackling innovation challenges:

- **Innovation Challenges** - It involves the setting of challenges and the design of potential solutions that take place at specific, formally defined moments, with the collaboration of academia and technology and innovation centres.
- **Innovation Room** - It helps to capture and conceptualise ideas for the design of solutions and their prioritisation, as well as, being a space equipped with tools for conducting feasibility analyses in collaboration with academia, research centres, startups and companies.
- **Train Lab Commercial** - It supports the analysis of the technical feasibility of solutions by carrying out pilot tests on passenger trains, reflecting real conditions of use, in collaboration with academia, research centres, start-ups and companies.
- **Train Lab Tech** - It supports the analysis of the technical feasibility of solutions by carrying out pilot tests on a laboratory train in a controlled environment, in collaboration with academia, research centres, start-ups, companies and transport operators.

Within the scope of **Innovation Challenges**, which involves setting challenges to academia and technology and innovation centres to design potential solutions, the Business model, according to the Business Model Canvas methodology, is characterised as follows:

Modelo de Negócio				
PARCEIROS ESTRATÉGICOS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academia e centros de tecnologia e inovação Entidades públicas e investidores Plataformas de <i>crowdsourcing</i> e inovação aberta 	ATIVIDADES CHAVE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lançamento de desafios de inovação Avaliação e seleção de propostas Implementação de soluções Gestão e acompanhamento de projetos 	PROPOSTA DE VALOR <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Desenvolvimento de soluções inovadoras Colaboração e cocriação Oportunidade para testes e validação 	RELAÇÃO COM CLIENTE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mentoria e suporte técnico Feedback contínuo Oportunidades de reconhecimento e implementação 	SEGMENTOS DE CLIENTE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academia; Centros de tecnologia e inovação; Trabalhadores da CP e Stakeholders Internos.
	RECURSOS CHAVE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Infraestruturas, plataforma e dados Capital humano Parcerias Financiamento 		CANAIS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plataforma digital de inovação Eventos de inovação (<i>Hackathons</i> e Maratonas de Ideias) Comunicação e redes sociais Parceiros com as entidades 	
ESTRUTURA DE CUSTOS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Custos fixos: Salários da equipa, despesas administrativas. Custos variáveis: Organização de eventos, divulgação e prémios associados. 		ESTRUTURA DE RECEITAS <p>Do ponto de vista de receitas e benefícios, temos as que decorrem de negócio e monetização propriamente dita do CP Lab, designadamente:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Realização de eventos para lançamento dos desafios de inovação (inclui <i>sponsorship</i>, taxas de inscrição/participação e benefícios das soluções obtidas/custo de oportunidade de fazer internamente). Financiamento de projetos de investigação aplicada. 		

9

Business Model (Modelo de Negócio)

- **Strategic partners (Parceiros estratégicos)**
 - Academia and technology and innovation centres
 - Public organisations and investors
 - Crowdsourcing and open innovation platforms
- **Key Activities (Atividades Chave)**
 - Launch of innovation challenges
 - Evaluation and selection of proposals
 - Implementation of solutions
 - Project management and monitoring
- **Key Features (Recursos Chave)**
 - Infrastructure, platform and data
 - Human capital
 - Partnerships
 - Financing
- **Cost structure (Estrutura de custos)**
 - **Fixed costs:** Staff salaries, administrative costs
 - **Variable costs:** Organising events, publicity and associated prizes

- **Value proposition (Proposta de valor)**
 - Development of innovative solutions
 - Collaboration and co-creation
 - Opportunities for testing and validation
- **Customer relations (Relação com clientes)**
 - Mentoring and technical support
 - Continuous feedback
 - Recognition and implementation opportunities
- **Channels (Channels)**
 - Digital innovation platform
 - Innovation events (Hackathons and Ideas Marathons)
 - Communication and social networks
 - Partnerships with organisations
- **Customer segments (Segmentos de cliente)**
 - Academy
 - Technology and innovation centres
 - CP employees and internal stakeholders
- **Revenue structures (Estruturas de receitas)**

From the point of view of revenues and benefits, we have those that derive from the business and monetisation itself of CP Lab, namely:

 - Organisation of events to launch innovation challenges (includes sponsorship, registration/participation fees and solution benefits).
 - Financing applied research projects

The main dimensions for implementing **Innovation Challenges** are as follows:

Identifying challenges and objectives (Identificação dos desafios e objetivos)

Mapping of challenges and alignment with strategy

Structuring the challenges (Estruturação dos desafios)

Sorting and creating challenge sheets

Strategic partnerships and financing (Parcerias estratégicas e financiamento)

Formalising partnerships and defining financing plans

Legal and intellectual property aspects (Aspectos legais e de propriedade intelectual)

Defining legal property management and analysing legal aspects

Platform, communication and dissemination (Plataforma, comunicação e divulgação)

Platform for publicising and advertising

Mentoring and continuous feedback (Mentoria e feedback contínuo)

Providing human resources and feedback

Implementing solutions (Implementing solutions)

Define implementation strategy for viable solutions

Evaluation and continuous improvement (Avaliação e melhoria contínua)

Evaluate opportunities for improvement for future editions

We have the most detailed information on this section, but for this stage we think it's enough to analyse and choose the topic to be developed. Depending on the choice, we can share more details.

Autistic persons autonomisation & inclusion residences

Esa Gustafsson, Tiia Manninen, Minna Sahlberg, Alicia Elie,
Eolia Mackoumbou-Nkouka & Maria Vlcekova

24/01/2025

inovarautismo.

Challenges

- 1 Promote independent living and autonomy for autistic people.
- 2 Analyze the situation now and find solutions for the future.

Our beneficiaries

Kris

14 years old
likes football and
swimming
doesn't like when his
dad cleans his room

Hannah

23 years old
likes music and animals
takes one hour to
choose her clothes

Gini

37 years old
likes to read and watch
movies
isolated and lonely
fear of dogs

Kris has first level of Autism

- **Characteristics:**

- Can communicate and function fairly independently but may face challenges in social situations and flexibility.
- Example: difficulties in initiating or maintaining conversations or adapting to changes in daily routines.

- **Support Needs:**

- Requires support, particularly in social interaction and handling changes in routines.

Hannah has second level of Autism

- **Characteristics:**

- More significant difficulties in social interaction and flexibility.
- Restricted and repetitive behaviors are more noticeable and may interfere with daily life.

- **Support Needs:**

- Substantial support is needed in daily life and social interaction, such as assistance with managing routines.

Gini has third level of Autism

- **Characteristics:**
 - Severe difficulties in social interaction and independent functioning.
 - Restricted behaviors and repetitive routines are very intense.
 - Communication difficulties are significant, often with very limited or no speech.
- **Support Needs:**
 - Requires continuous and extensive support in daily life and social interaction.

OUR JOURNEY

Our research

***Innovative Real
Estate Technologies***

AI Systems & ASC

***Visual Information
Processing***

***Robotics and AI
Agents***

Technical tools

Robots

supporting the learning of social skills + motivation through technology

Apps for autism + AI

easily available, simplifying communication

Intelligent home

supporting daily life and independence

I. Applications

Supporting the learning of social skills + motivation through technology

- **How it works:** Users can create daily schedules visually by adding pictures, colors, and reminders.
- **Example:** A person who struggles to understand the flow of the day can create a schedule with images of breakfast, commuting to school, and hobbies, making the day's structure clearer.

For communication support: Proloquo2Go

- **How it works:** The app uses picture symbols and text-to-speech functionality to help individuals who have difficulty with verbal communication.
- **Example:** A person can tap on a picture of food, and the app says, "I want to eat." This helps ensure clear communication, especially in high-pressure situations.

For motivation and assistance: Habitica

- **How it works:** Turns daily tasks into a game where users earn rewards such as points or virtual items for completing tasks.
- **Example:** A user adds a task like "do homework" and earns rewards after completing it, making daily routines fun and engaging.

	←	zzz	 Estoy yendo a comer			
					ahora 	
yo 						
	de	a				
ella/eso 	el	un				
nosotros/as 	y	con				
	poder	acciones 				

Grid 3

Grid 3 by Smartbox is AAC software for individuals with communication challenges, including autistic users.

Features:

- Customizable symbol/text grids
- Text-to-speech in multiple languages
- Interactive learning tools
- Computer access
- Visual schedules

AI integration with Grid 3

Improve communication for users by enhancing efficiency, personalization and context awareness.

II. Intelligent home

For control smart home devices, and access information: Google Home

- **How it works:** Google Home lets users control lighting, temperature, and sound via voice or mobile app, integrating with smart devices to create personalized routines.
- **Example:** A user can set a "Relaxing Time" routine where Google Home dims the lights, adjusts the temperature, and plays calming music. The system can also adjust settings based on mood cues, such as signs of stress.

III. Robotic pets and humanoids

Technology should be designed to be simple and intuitive, allowing individuals with autism to fully benefit from its features and enhance their daily lives.

Thank you for your attention!

